

Study of 5,10-diphenyl-5H-[1,2,4]triazolo[4',3':4,5][1,3,4]thiadiazolo[3,2-a] pyrido [3,2-f] quinazolines

Himanshu Sharma¹, Ranjana Dubey^{2*}, Tilak Ram³

¹Department of Chemistry, M.I.E.T, Meerut, U.P., India

²Department of Chemistry, S.R.M. University, Modinagar, Ghaziabad, U. P., India

³Department of Chemistry, Govt. P.G. College, Uttarkashi, U.K., India

*Corresponding author: Ranjana Dubey, E-mail: ranjana.srm@india.com

Received: August 2, 2014, Accepted: September 3, 2014, Published: September 4, 2014.

ABSTRACT

Present study consists of design, synthesis of several novel substituted [3,2-f]quinazolines derivatives (3a-e) and antibacterial and antifungal evaluation. The structures of the synthesized derivatives were evaluated by IR, ¹H-NMR, Mass and elemental analysis (C, H, N). Compound 3b showed significant antimicrobial spectrum.

Keywords: substituted [3,2-f]quinazolines, antibacterial, antifungal.

INTRODUCTION

Bacterial threatening to society as multi-drug resistance is a big blow and continual drug development program is the only solution. Literature study explored the role of heterocyclic derivatives in the field of medicinal chemistry viz. 1,3,4-thiadiazole [1-4], quinoline [5-6] and triazoles [7-10] were found of great significance due to their versatile biological activities. 3-Phenyl substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles were found of great interest due to their ambient nucleophilic centre and generally employed as starting materials/molecular manipulation for the synthesis of several interesting potent N-bridged heterocycles. In the current work designing and synthesis was focused on 1,3,4-thiadiazole, quinoline and triazole moieties. By adopting the conventional synthetic strategies several substituted 1,3,4-thiadiazoles were synthesised with the hope that the synthesised derivatives will better biological profile with the minimum amount of toxicity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis was started by the reaction of quinolin-5-ol, acetophenone and urea to yield compound **1**, which on further refluxing with phosphorous oxychloride furnished compound **2**. Condensation reaction of compound **2** and 5,10-diphenyl-5H-[1,2,4]triazolo[4',3':4,5][1,3,4]thiadiazolo[3,2-a]pyrido [3,2-f]quinazolines **3a-e**. The synthesized compounds **2** and **3a-e** were biologically evaluated for antibacterial and antifungal activity against the selected strains of pathogens (Table-1 & 2). The screened derivatives **2** and **3a-e** fungistatic activity at 1.10-360 $\mu\text{mol/ml}$ while fungicidal activity was achieved at 2.15-745.2 $\mu\text{mol/ml}$. Among all the tested derivatives, compound **3b** exhibited the highest antifungal potential with MIC at $1.12-2.19 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{mol/ml}$ and MFC at 2.18.15-4.30 $\mu\text{mol/ml}$. All the compounds showed brawny antibacterial activity against all bacterial species. MIC for the compounds **2** and **3a-e** were at $0.65-74.5 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{mol/ml}$ and MBC

1.15-125.5 $\times 10^{-2} \mu\text{mol/ml}$. This compound showed the best antifungal as well as antibacterial effect among all the tested. Reference drugs were ampicillin (MIC 3.5–25.8 $\times 10^{-2} \mu\text{mol/ml}$ and MBC 8.6–51.6 $\times 10^{-2} \mu\text{mol/ml}$) and ketoconazole (MIC 0.60–2.38 $\times 10^{-2} \mu\text{mol/ml}$ and MFC 2.38–3.35 $\times 10^{-2} \mu\text{mol/ml}$) for antibacterial and antifungal activity respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used for the preparation of desired derivatives, were obtained from Sisco Research Laboratories (SRL), Mumbai, India; Qualigen Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India; E. Merck Ltd., New Delhi, India. The reference drugs ampicillin and ketoconazole were procured from Ind-Swift, Pharmaceutical, Panjab, India. The melting points of the compounds were determined in open glass capillaries with the help of thermionic melting points apparatus (Campbell Electronics, Mumbai, India) and are uncorrected. The homogeneity of all the newly synthesized compounds was routinely checked by TLC on silica gel G plates and spots were located by using iodine chamber. Elemental analysis was performed in Heraeus CHN rapid analyser. The results were found within the $\pm 0.4\%$ of theoretical values. Infrared spectra were recorded on KBr pellets on a Perkin Elmer system 2000 FTIR spectrometer and ¹H-NMR spectra on Bruker DPX 200 using TMS as internal standard.

PHARMACOLOGY

All the newly synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against the clinically isolated and identified microbial strains. The antibacterial assay was carried out by micro dilution method [12-14] while modified micro dilution technique [12-11] was used for the antifungal activity. The minimum inhibitory, bactericidal and fungicidal concentrations (MICs, MBCs and MFCs) were determined by a serial dilution technique using 96-well microtiter plates.

TABLE 1: Antifungal activity of tested compounds (3a-e) (MIC & MFC in $\mu\text{mol/ml} \times 10^{-2}$)

Bacterial strains	Compound 2 MIC MBC	Compound 3a MIC MBC	Compound 3b MIC MBC	Compound 3c MIC MBC	Compound 3d MIC MBC	Compound 3e MIC MBC
<i>B. cereus</i>	74.5 125.2	1.68 2.24	0.65 1.15	2.15 4.10	2.00 2.71	2.00 2.68
<i>S. aureus</i> (ATCC)	37.4 49.5	1.15 2.19	0.80 1.45	1.61 2.15	1.72 2.29	1.30 3.36
<i>E. coli</i>	70.5 122	1.20 1.64	1.08 2.15	2.08 4.20	1.15 2.29	1.70 2.18
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	74.5 125.5	1.10 2.19	1.24 2.60	1.10 2.19	1.79 2.38	1.64 4.38

TABLE 2: Antibacterial activity of the tested compounds (3a-e) (MIC & MBC in $\mu\text{mol/ml} \times 10^{-2}$)

Fungal strains	Compound 2 MIC MFC	Compound 3a MIC MFC	Compound 3b MIC MFC	Compound 3c MIC MFC	Compound 3d MIC MFC	Compound 3e MIC MFC
<i>A. niger</i>	285 660	1.12 2.22	1.10 2.15	1.64 4.38	2.10 6.15	2.14 4.40
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	280 665	2.19 4.38	1.65 4.20	2.20 4.45	1.65 4.32	1.62 4.15
<i>C. albicans</i>	360 740	2.12 4.41	2.19 4.38	2.15 4.35	2.25 6.42	2.26 4.50
<i>C. crusei</i>	360 745.2	4.40 6.57	2.19 4.38	4.42 6.58	4.25 6.24	4.30 6.45

continuous stirring, filtered and recrystallized by methanol: Yield: 66%; m.p.: 175 °C; R_f : 0.66. IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3410 (NH), 1745 (C=O), 1625 (C...C of aromatic ring), 1590 (C=N), 1290 (C-O-C). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , δ/ppm): 8.60-7.42 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 6.78 (bs, 1H, NH), 4.70 (s, 1H, CH-NH). Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 73.90; H, 4.38; N, 10.14; found C, 73.42; H, 4.35; N, 10.20. MS (m/z): 276.09.

Preparation of 3-chloro-1-phenyl-1H-[1,3]oxazino [5,6-f]quinoline (2)

Phosphorous oxychloride (0.015 mol) added slowly to a solution of compound 1 (0.01 mol) in toluene. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. Excess of solvent was distilled off. The reaction mixture cooled. The cooled mass poured into ice-water slowly with continuous stirring, neutralized with aqueous 3% KOH solution, filtered and recrystallized by methanol: Yield: 61%; m.p.: 213 °C; R_f : 0.70. IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1622 (C...C of aromatic ring), 1594 (C=N), 1288 (C-O-C). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , δ/ppm): 8.52-7.55 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 4.75 (s, 1H, CH-N-C). Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}$: C, 69.28; H, 3.76; N, 9.50; found C, 69.31; H, 3.80; N, 9.63. MS (m/z): 294.06.

General preparation of 5,10-diphenyl-5H- [1,2,4]triazolo [4',3':4,5][1,3,4]thiadiazolo[3,2-a]pyrido [3,2-f]quinazolines (3a-e)

The solution of compound 2 (0.002 mol) in isopropanol was refluxed with 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.002 mol) for 2-3 hours. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the reaction mixture thus obtained was cooled, poured into ice cold water, washed with petroleum ether (40-60°C) and recrystallised with appropriate solvents to furnish the products 3a-e. Compound 3a:

SCHEME-1

SYNTHESIS

Preparation of 1-phenyl-1H-[1,3]oxazino[5,6-f]quinolin-3(2H)one (1)

A mixture of quinolin-5-ol (0.01 mol), urea (0.01 mol) and acetophenone (0.01 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice-water slowly with

Yield: 68%; m.p.: 240 °C; R_f: 0.76. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1620 (C...C of aromatic ring), 1591 (C=N), 1369(N-N), 1292 (C-O-C), 670 (C-S-C). ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, δ/ppm): 8.55-7.20 (m, 15H, Ar-H), 4.56 (s, 1H, CH-N-C). Anal. calcd. for C₂₅H₁₆N₆S: C, 69.43; H,3.73; N, 19.43; found C, 69.38; H,3.67; N,19.58. MS (m/z): 432.12.

CONCLUSION

All the screened derivatives displayed mild to moderate antimicrobial profile but derivative **3b** displayed significant antifungal and antibacterial profiles. Biological data revealed that the diverse substitution was well abided on the substituted [3,2-f]quinazolines for proper fit at the potential receptor site and 4-chlorophenyl substitution enhanced biological activities. It provided broad antifungal as well as antibacterial spectrum to the substituted [3,2-f]quinazolines.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We are thankful for SAIF, Punjab University, India for spectral and elemental analysis.

REFERENCES

1. Kadi A. A., El-Brollosy N. R., Al-Deeb O. A., Habib E. E., Ibrahim T. M. and El-Emam A. A. 2007. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 42: 235-242.
2. Kumar D., Maruthi N. K., Chang K. H. and Shah K. 2010. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 45(10): 4664-4668.
3. Aggarwal N., Kumar R., Dureja P. and Khurana J. M. 2012. *Chem. Bio. & Drug Des.* 79(4): 384–397.
4. Mullican M. D., Wilson M. W., Conner D. T., Kostlan C. R., Schrier D. J. and Dyer R. D. 1993. *J. Med. Chem.*, 36 (8): 1090–1099.
5. El-Sayed O. A., Al-Turki T. M., Al-Daffiri H. M., Al-Bassam B. A. and Hussein M. E. 2004. *Boll Chim Farm.* 143(6): 227-238.
6. Hongmanee P., Rukseree K., Buabut B., Somsri B. and Palittapongarnpim P. 2007. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 51(3): 1105–1106.
7. Nadkarni B.A., Kamat V.R. and Khadse B.G. 2001. *Arzneim. Forsch.* 51: 569–573.
8. Isloor A.M., Kalluraya B. and Shetty P. 2009. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 44: 3784–3787.
9. Mange Y. J., Isloor, A. M., Malladi, S., Isloor S. and Fun H.-K. 2013. *Arab. J. Chem.* 6: 177–181.
10. Panwar. H. and Singh S. 2011. *Indo. J. Chem.* 11 (2): 148 – 153.
11. Mullick P., Khan S. A., Verma S. and Alam O. 2010. *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.* 31: 2345-2350.
12. Norris, J. R., Ribbons, D. W., Eds. 1971. *Fungal Culture Media*. In *Methods in Microbiology Academic Press: New York IV*: 49–94.
13. Daouk K. D., Dagher M. S. and Sattout J. E. 1995. *J. Food Prot.* 58: 1147-1149.
14. Hanel H. and Raether W. 1988. *Mycoses* 3: 148-154.
15. Espinel-Ingroff A. 2001. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 39 (4): 1360-1367.

Citation: Ranjana Dubey, et al (2014), Study of 5,10-diphenyl-5H-[1,2,4]triazolo[4',3':4,5][1,3,4]thiadiazolo[3,2-a]pyrido[3,2-f]quinazolines. *J. of Modern Drug Discovery and Drug Delivery Research*. V2I1. DOI: 10.15297/JMDDR.V2I1.02

Copyright: © 2014 Ranjana Dubey. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.